

Activated Nitrile in Heterocyclic Synthesis. A Novel Synthesis of Pyrazolo[3,4-*b*]pyridine, Pyrrolo[2,3-*c*]pyrazole, Pyrano[2,-3*c*]pyrazole and Pyrrolo[3,4-*c*]pyrazole

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The hydrazidoyl halides (2a-c) react with 2-amino-1,1,3-tricyano-1-propene (1a), diethyl 3-amino-2-cyano-2-pentene-1,5-dicarboxylate (1b), 3-iminobutanonitrile (1c), succinonitrile, 1,3-dicyano-2-iminopropane and 1,3-dicyanoacetone in sodium ethoxide solution to give the corresponding pyrazolo[3,4-*b*]pyridine (6), pyrano[2,3-*c*]pyrazole (7), pyrazole (10), pyrrolo[2,3-*c*]pyrazole (11), pyrazolo[3,4-*b*]pyridine (16) and pyrazole derivatives (20), respectively. The structural assignments have been made on the basis of the elemental analysis and spectral data. The reaction mechanism was suggested as alkylation reaction. Also two molecules of 2 were reacted with succinonitrile and 1,3-dicyanoacetone in the same previous conditions to give the pyrazolyl pyrazole (13) and dipyrazolylketone (21), respectively. The structural assignments were suggested based on elemental analysis and spectral data.

HYDRAZIDOYL halides are reactive intermediates and their utility in heterocyclic synthesis has drawn considerable attention^{1,2}. In continuation of our program directed for the development of new procedures for synthesis of fused azoles³⁻⁸, the present work is a part of the program to explore the synthetic potentiality, scope and limitation of the utility of polyfunctional nitriles in heterocyclic synthesis. This paper deals with the behaviour of the enamino nitrile derivative (1a-c), succinonitrile, 1,3-dicyano-2-iminopropane and 1,3-dicyanoacetone towards the hydrazidoyl halides (2a-c). Thus when 1a is subjected to the action of 2a, a product having molecular formula C₂₀H₁₄N₇OCl is obtained. Several isomeric possible structures are considered (Scheme 1). The ir spectra of the product exhibit only one conjugated cyano absorption band, a matter which prefers the cyclic structure 6 to the other acyclic ones containing more than one cyano group. The formation of 6 is assumed to proceed either via 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition or preferably via nucleophilic substitution on the highly activated methylene group of 1a. Successive cyclisation rearrangements of the acyclic intermediate 4 will lead to the final product 6 (Scheme 1). The acyclic intermediate 3 which may be produced by substitution on the amino group of 1a is ruled out according to the fact that it can not cyclise to yield 6. Attempts to isolate the intermediates are fruitless. The reaction of 1b with 2b is also investigated where the pyrano[2,3-*c*]pyrazole derivative (7) is obtained. Logically, compound 7 is produced either through a dipolar cycloaddition or nucleophilic substitution at the active methylene group of 1b followed by successive

elimination of two molecules of ethanol (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

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Though the isolation of acyclic intermediates are unsuccessful in the preceding reactions, yet we isolated the acyclic intermediate 9 from the reaction of 1c with 2c. Compound 9 and not 8 is suggested to be the product according to the ir data which clarifies two NH absorption bands. An additional evidence for compound 9 is attained by acid hydrolysis where compound 10 is obtained. Hydrolysis of 8 does not lead to 10, so structure 8 is ruled out.

Condensation of 2c with succinonitrile in equimolar amounts yields the pyrrolo[2,3-c]pyrazole derivative (11). The structure of 11 is inferred from analytical data and ir data where the cyano absorption disappeared. It seemed also most likely that 11 has been formed via stepwise alkylation on the methylene group followed by cyclisation under the same reaction conditions. On the other hand, when two molecules of 2c reacted with one molecule of succinonitrile, a product with molecular formula $C_{24}H_{18}N_6O_4Cl_2$ was obtained. Two isomeric possible structures (12 and 13) are considered (Scheme 2). The triazole 13 may be produced

ruled out based on the ir data which reveal absorption bands of amino groups.

Similarly, the behaviour of 2c toward other polyactivated nitriles under the same reaction conditions is also studied. When 2c reacts with 1,3-dicyano-2-iminopropane the pyrazole derivative 15 is obtained through the alkylation reaction of the methylene group followed by cyclic rearrangement. More cyclisation of 15 is achieved by the action of concentrated H_2SO_4 to give 16.

The action of 1-phenylazo-1,3-dicyano-2-iminopropane on 2c affords the pyrrolo[3,4-c]pyrazole (17). The structure of 17 is supported by the ir spectra which reveal the presence of one cyano band and the absence of the ester group. In this reaction, it was expected to obtain the phenylazo derivative 16, but this was not the case. To account for this result, it is supposed that steric factors due to the presence of phenylazo group hindered the cyclisation process. Another pathway of cyclisation takes place via the imino and the ester groups where loss of one molecule of ethanol gives rise to 17.

Finally, the reaction between 2c and 1,3-dicyanoacetone in equimolar amounts gives rise to a product with the molecular formula $C_{18}H_{18}N_4O_8Cl$. The ir spectra show only one cyano band, which is consistent with the structure 20, thus structures 18 and 19 are excluded. The formation of 20 is assumed to proceed via stepwise alkylation rather than a concerted cycloaddition to afford the acyclic intermediate 19 followed by cyclisation under the same reaction conditions.

When the reaction of 2c and 1,3-dicyanoacetone is repeated in the ratio 2:1, respectively, we obtained the dipyrzoyl ketone (21), the structure of which is supported by the ir spectra which revealed amino group bands.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Pye-Unicam SP-1100 spectrophotometer. Analytical data were obtained from the Cairo Analytical Center at Cairo University. Analytical, physical and spectral data of the compounds are given in Table 1.

General method to prepare compounds 6, 7, 10, 11, 15, 17 and 20: To an ethanolic sodium ethoxide solution (prepared from 0.01 mol sodium metal and 30 ml ethanol) was added 0.01 mol of 2-amino-1,1,3-tricyano-1-propene or diethyl-3-amino-2-cyano-2-pentene-1,5-dicarboxylate or 3-iminobutanonitrile or succinonitrile or 1,3-dicyano-2-iminopropane or 1-phenylazo-2-imino-1,3-dicyanopropane and or 1,3-dicyanoacetone. After stirring the resulting solution for 3 min at room temperature, the corresponding hydrazidoyl halides (2a-c; 0.01 mol) was added to it and the stirring continued for 2 h, and the reaction mixture left overnight at room temperature. The reaction mixture was then poured

Scheme 2

via 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition while structure 12 is suggested via alkylation reaction. Structure 13 is

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Compd. no.	M.p. ^a C°	Yield %	Mol. formula/ (Mol. weight)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				ν_{max} cm ⁻¹ (Selected bands)
				C	H	N	Cl	
6a	118 ^a	55	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₇ OCl (403.5)	59.2 (59.4)	3.3 (3.4)	24.1 (24.2)	8.7 (8.7)	1 710 (ester), 2 220 (CN), 3 000 (CH), 3 100–3 490 (NH ₂)
7b	90 ^a	52	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ (306)	66.5 (66.6)	4.3 (4.5)	18.1 (18.3)		1 660–1 730 (C=O, ester), 2 215 (CN), 3 000 (CH), 3 200–3 500 (NH ₂)
9c	115 ^b	58	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₂ Cl (306.5)	54.5 (54.8)	4.6 (4.8)	18.0 (18.2)	11.4 (11.5)	1 700 (ester), 2 215 (CN), 3 000 (CH), 3 220–3 245 (NH, NH ₂)
10c	250 ^a	40	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ Cl (307.5)	54.4 (54.6)	4.4 (4.5)	13.3 (13.6)	11.3 (11.5)	1 680–1 770 (CONH ₂ , ester), 3 000 (CH)
11c	85 ^a	60	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₂ Cl (304.5)	54.9 (55.1)	4.1 (4.2)	18.1 (18.3)	11.3 (11.6)	1 700 (ester), 2 900–3 000 (CH), 3 300–3 500 (NH ₂)
12c	132 ^b	68	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₂ Cl ₂ (529)	54.1 (54.4)	3.9 (4.1)	15.5 (15.8)	13.3 (13.4)	1 730, 1 750 (2 esters), 3 000 (CH), 3 150–3 500 (NH ₂)
15c	188 ^a	62	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₅ O ₂ Cl (331.5)	54.1 (54.2)	4.1 (4.2)	20.8 (21.1)	10.5 (10.7)	1 725 (ester), 2 215 (CN), 3 000 (CH), 3 100–3 550 (NH ₂)
16c	250 ^a	45	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₅ O ₂ Cl (331.5)	54.0 (54.2)	3.9 (4.2)	20.9 (21.1)	10.6 (10.7)	1 710 (ester), 3 000 (CH), 3 150–3 350 (NH ₂)
17c	125 ^a	52	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₆ OCl (389.5)	58.6 (58.5)	2.8 (3.0)	24.8 (25.1)	9.1 (9.1)	1 650 (C=O), 2 222 (CCN), 3 000 (CH), 3 100–3 600 (NH, NH ₂)
20c	157 ^a	60	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₂ Cl (332.5)	53.9 (54.1)	3.8 (3.9)	16.5 (16.8)	10.4 (10.6)	1 650 (C=O), 1 710 (ester), 2 215 (CN), 3 000 (CH), 3 100–3 350 (NH ₂)
21c	110 ^b	52	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₂ Cl (321.5)	57.4 (57.5)	4.0 (4.2)	15.8 (16.1)	13.5 (13.6)	1 710–1 750 (C=O, ester), 3 000 (CH)

^aSolvent of crystallisation ; ^aethanol, ^bbenzene – petroleum ether.

into ice-water, a few drops of dilute HCl was added if no precipitate was formed. The solid product was collected and recrystallised from suitable solvent to give compounds 6, 7, 10, 11, 15, 17 and 20, respectively.

Cyclisation of compounds 9 and 15 to compounds 10 and 16, respectively: Compound 9 or 15 was heated with concentrated H₂SO₄ until dissolved, then the reaction mixture was left for 2 h at room temperature. The reaction mixture was poured into ice, if no precipitate was formed then solution of Na₂CO₃ was added. The resulting solid was collected by filtration and crystallisation from ethanol gave compounds 10 and 16, respectively (Table 1).

Method of preparation of pyrazolopyrazole (12) and dipyrazolyl ketone (21): To an ethanolic sodium ethoxide solution (0.02 mol) was added succinonitrile (0.01 mol) or 1,3-dicyanoacetone (0.01 mol). The reaction mixture was stirred for 3 min at room temperature, then ethyl chloroglyoxalate-*p*-chlorophenylhydrazone (2c; 0.02 mol) was added and the stirring continued for 5 h, and the reaction mixture left overnight at room temperature. The reaction mixture was poured into cold water with a few drops of dilute HCl. The resulting solid was filtered and crystallised from the proper solvent to give the compounds 12

and 21, respectively. The elemental analysis and spectral data are recorded in Table 1.

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